

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE OVERHANG INTERPROXIMAL
AMALGAM PREVALENCE AND ITS RESTORATION BY
UNDER GRADUATE STUDENTS*****Dr. Ujala Arshad, *Dr. Hifza Niazi, *Dr. Saba Riaz, *Dr. Sara Izhar, *Dr. Mohsin Majeed**
*Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan**Abstract:**

Periodontal structures are vital tissues that can be affected by the environment. Dental materials and / or restorations may trigger a negative reaction such as gingivitis and bone loss of periodontal tissues.

Objective: *The aim of this analysis is to determine the overhang interproximal amalgam prevalence and its restoration by undergraduate students.*

Study design: *A stratified random sampling technique.*

Location and Duration: *In the Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan for six months duration from January 2018 to June 2018.*

Methods: *For analysis 32 patients (male) between 18-43 years were selected randomly. 966 proximal surfaces and Posterior bitewing radiographs were taken and were evaluated. For data analysis SPSS version 17.0 was used. To evaluate the association between the surface of the overhang and location, Chi-square test was used.*

Results: *It was determined that 34% of the 206 surfaces restored with amalgam were hanged. Among the upper amalgam restorations, 26.91% in the lower posterior teeth and 73.0% were in the upper posterior teeth. In amalgam examinations, mesial were 57.1% and distal were 42.9%. There was no vast variation in the amalgam restorations prevalence between premolar (46.91%) and molars (53.09%) ($P > 0.05$).*

Conclusion: *This study clearly defined the high prevalence of significant interproximal margins in amalgam restorations.*

Key words: *periodontal destruction, amalgam overhang, dental amalgam.*

Corresponding author:***Dr. Ujala Arshad,***Nishtar Institute of Dentistry,
Multan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ujala Arshad et al., **Study to Know the Overhang Interproximal Amalgam Prevalence and Its Restoration By Under Graduate Students.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Overhang interproximal restorations have been observed for a long time as a causing factor to periodontal loss and gingivitis. Restorations are a major concern because their prevalence is estimated to be 26-77% for all restored surfaces. In general, exceptional restorations are thought to contribute to gingivitis due to their ability to hold plaques. Gilmore et al. (1971) showed interproximal radiographic bone loss associated with proximal restorations in posterior teeth. In 1980 Jeffcoat, et al determined hundred females of overhang and without overhang 100 cases were selected. They reported much bone loss with large overhang around the teeth. but; Small overhang was not linked with bone loss. Lang et al. (1983) in addition also investigated the local bacterial accumulation and its specific aspects linked with overhang restorations. The subgingival placement extensions caused changes in microflora linked with those noted in chronic periodontitis in adults. The ratio of gram-negative anaerobic bars, especially black pigmented bacteriodes, has been increased. Therefore, the suspended restorations not only raise the plaque size but also lead to certain periodontal pathogens increase in the plaque. In addition, they may result in damage by affecting their buried areas and biological width. The aim of this analysis is to explain the overhang interproximal amalgam prevalence and by undergraduate students its restorations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This stratified random sampling technique analysis was held in the Nishtar Institute of Dentistry Multan for six months duration from January 2018 to June 2018. 35 male patients were selected randomly between of 18 and 43 years of age. Posterior bitewing radiographs were obtained using 70 kilovolts (peak) [kV (p)] and 7 mA 70 X-ray units (SIEMENS® Heliudent model, Germany). The 0.20 seconds was the exposure time. A total of 966 proximal surfaces were evaluated from which the amalgam surface was recovered. 3rd molars, superimposed proximal surfaces and teeth opposite to the cavities were removed from the analysis. At the Faculty of Dentistry, undergraduate students performed all restorations. A doctor took an examination and in a dark room under standard conditions Radiographs were examined using a fixed light source in an X-ray viewer. Using SPSS Version # 17, the data was analyzed. To evaluate the relationship between the prevalence of overhang surfaces and its location, Chi-square test was used.

RESULTS:

We examined 483 female radiographs of 966 proximal surfaces and sixty-nine posterior bones, of which with amalgam 206 were restored. With amalgam, 206 proximal surfaces were restored 71 (33.90%) had significant limits. When overhang restorations were compared between the upper and lower teeth, 50 (73.09%) of the upper posterior teeth had amalgam margins in the lower posterior teeth compared to only 19 (27.1%) (Table 1).

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTIONS OF THE AMALGAM OVERHANGS

	Percentage	Number	P-value
Upper	72.9	51	0.029
Lower	27.1	19	
Mesial	57.1	40	0.440
Distal	42.9	30	
Premolar	47.1	33	0.773
Molar	52.9	37	

On the amalgam examinations, mesial were noted in 57.1% and distal in 42.9%. The variation was not significant statistically ($P > 0.6$) [Table 1]. Similarly, there was no vast variation in the overhang amalgam prevalence restorations between premolar (46.91%) and molars (53.09%) ($P > 0.05$) [Table 1]. The overhang highest prevalence margins on the upper molars mesial surfaces was 30%. On the lower molars on the distal surfaces, the minimum prevalence was (4.3%).

The overhang amalgam margins prevalence on mesial surfaces of premolars was higher in upper teeth (15.03%) than in lower teeth (6.91%). On the other side, the amalgam prevalence on the premolar distal surfaces was higher in the upper teeth (16.07%) than in the lower teeth (11%). Grinding stones; The incidence of the overhang on the molars mesial surfaces was greater than the lower teeth (6.07%) and the incidence of the overhang on the molar teeth in the distal surfaces was higher than the premolar teeth (13.09%) (3.93% lower) [fig1].

Fig 1: Distribution of the amalgam overhangs according to the surfaces

DISCUSSION:

There is no doubt about the destructive effects of continuous repair limits in periodontal support. Recently, Roman-Torres et al. (2006) and Mokeem (2007) reported the effect of tooth extraction on periodontal parameters. (2007) Mokeem Amalgam reported a significant reduction in GI and the depth of the bag after removing the restorations of gingival intestinal fluid, projections.

The prevalence of selective amalgam margins (34%) was lower than other studies; Hakkaranein and Ainamo6 (50%), Sikri Sikri (64.12%), Lervic arc.8 (87%), Gorzo et al. 9 (74%), Wright10 (57%), Coxhead11 (76%) and Coxhead et al. 12 (52%). The difference is attributable to the fact that the current sample obtains the dental school, where all procedures are expected to be supervised by teaching dentistry; Previous examples were taken from general dentist clinics. The overhangs were higher in the upper teeth, which can be attributed to the increased accessibility of the lower teeth during restoration in connection with amalgam upper teeth. There was no statistical difference between the amalgam prevalence of mesial and distal surfaces; Relatively small sample size between molars and premolars.

CONCLUSION:

- This study determined the high overhang prevalence of high-range in amalgam restorations.
- Prevention, recognition and amalgam restoration are necessary to minimize the risk for periodontal disease, giving greater importance to the immediate elimination of outstanding margins.

REFERENCES:

1. Baharlooei, Kheyzeran, Nasim Hashemi, Mohsen Azad, and Sajad Ansari Fard. "Evaluation the Overhang Rate in Class II Amalgam Restorations among Bandar Abbas Patients in 2015." *Journal of Research in Medical and Dental Science* 6, no. 1 (2018): 151-156.
2. Ghulam, Omar A., and Hani T. Fadel. "Can clusters based on caries experience and medical status explain the distribution of overhanging dental restorations and recurrent caries? A cross-sectional study in Madinah-Saudi Arabia." *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* 25, no. 2 (2018): 367-371.
3. Ahmad, Muhammad, Rahul Gaikwad, and Bilal Arjumand. "Comparison of two different matrix

- band systems in restoring two surface cavities in posterior teeth done by senior undergraduate students at Qassim University, Saudi Arabia: A randomized controlled clinical trial." *Indian Journal of Dental Research* 29, no. 4 (2018): 459-459.
4. Signori, Cácia, Mark Laske, Fausto M. Mendes, Marie-Charlotte DNJM Huysmans, Maximiliano S. Cenci, and Niek JM Opdam. "Decision-making of general practitioners on interventions at restorations based on bitewing radiographs." *Journal of dentistry* 76 (2018): 109-116.
 5. Katafuchi, Michitsuna, Bradley F. Weinstein, Brian G. Leroux, Yen-Wei Chen, and Diane M. Daubert. "Restoration contour is a risk indicator for peri-implantitis: A cross-sectional radiographic analysis." *Journal of clinical periodontology* 45, no. 2 (2018): 225-232.
 6. Köken, Serhat, Jelena Juloski, Roberto Sorrentino, Simone Grandini, and Marco Ferrari. "Marginal sealing of relocated cervical margins of mesio-occluso-distal overlays." *Journal of oral science* (2018): 17-0331.
 7. Mahtani, Anisha A., and Ganesh Jeevanandan. "Retention of plaque in two commercially available stainless steel crowns-an in vivo study." *Drug Invention Today* 10, no. 8 (2018). Mahtani, A. A., & Jeevanandan, G. (2018). Retention of plaque in two commercially available stainless steel crowns-an in vivo study. *Drug Invention Today*, 10(8).
 8. Lynch, C. D., D. J. J. Farnell, H. Stanton, I. G. Chestnutt, P. A. Brunton, and N. H. F. Wilson. "No more amalgams: Use of amalgam and amalgam alternative materials in primary dental care." *British dental journal* 225, no. 2 (2018): 171. Lynch, C. D., Farnell, D. J. J., Stanton, H., Chestnutt, I. G., Brunton, P. A., & Wilson, N. H. F. (2018). No more amalgams: Use of amalgam and amalgam alternative materials in primary dental care. *British dental journal*, 225(2), 171.
 9. French, David, Marie-Catherine French, Bernie Linke, and Joseph Lizotte. "Two-Center Observational Case Series Describing Decay Adjacent to Fixed Implant Restorations (DATFIR) and Evaluation of Case Parameters." *Global Journal of Oral Science* 4 (2018): 32-41.
 10. Bruckmann, Corinna, and Gernot Wimmer. "Gingival Recession: Clinical Examination and Diagnostics." In *Gingival Recession Management*, pp. 33-50. Springer, Cham, 2018. Bruckmann, C., & Wimmer, G. (2018). Gingival Recession: Clinical Examination and Diagnostics. In *Gingival Recession Management* (pp. 33-50). Springer, Cham.
 11. Abrams, Tamara, Stephen Abrams, Koneswaran Sivagurunathan, Veronika Moravan, Warren Hellen, Gary Elman, Bennett Amaechi, and Andreas Mandelis. "Detection of Caries Around Resin-Modified Glass Ionomer and Compomer Restorations Using Four Different Modalities In Vitro." *Dentistry journal* 6, no. 3 (2018): 47.
 12. Ergin, E., Z. B. Kutuk, F. Y. Cakir, and S. Gurgan. "Comparison of two different composite resins used for tooth reshaping and diastema closure in a 4-year follow-up." *Nigerian journal of clinical practice* 21, no. 9 (2018): 1098-1106. Ergin, E., Kutuk, Z. B., Cakir, F. Y., & Gurgan, S. (2018). Comparison of two different composite resins used for tooth reshaping and diastema closure in a 4-year follow-up. *Nigerian journal of clinical practice*, 21(9), 1098-1106.
 13. Koleventi, Aikaterini, Dimitra Sakellari, Konstantinos N. Arapostathis, and Nikolaos Kotsanos. "Periodontal Impact of Preformed Metal Crowns on Permanent Molars of Children and Adolescents: A Pilot Study." *Pediatric dentistry* 40, no. 2 (2018): 117-121. Koleventi, A., Sakellari, D., Arapostathis, K. N., & Kotsanos, N. (2018). Periodontal Impact of Preformed Metal Crowns on Permanent Molars of Children and Adolescents: A Pilot Study. *Pediatric dentistry*, 40(2), 117-121.
 14. Scarfe, William C., Bruno Azevedo, Lucas Rodrigues Pinheiro, Menik Priaminiari, and Marcelo Augusto Oliveira Sales. "Periodontal Disease." In *Maxillofacial Cone Beam Computed Tomography*, pp. 923-949. Springer, Cham, 2018. Scarfe, W. C., Azevedo, B., Pinheiro, L. R., Priaminiari, M., & Sales, M. A. O. (2018). Periodontal Disease. In *Maxillofacial Cone Beam Computed Tomography* (pp. 923-949). Springer, Cham.
 15. PALONE, M. V. CIRURGIA PARENDODÔNTICA-UMA VISÃO PANORÂMICA. PALONE, MARIANA VICENTINI. "CIRURGIA PARENDODÔNTICA-UMA VISÃO PANORÂMICA."